

Clinico-Etiological Profile of Neonatal Seizures in Term NeonatesVivekanand Paul¹, Rakesh Kumar^{2*}, N P Gupta³¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laherasarai Bihar, India.²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laherasarai Bihar, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Laherasarai, Bihar, India.

Received: 14-01-2024 / Revised: 11-02-2024 / Accepted: 10-03-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Rakesh Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Neonatal seizures or neonatal convulsions are epileptic fits occurring from birth to the end of the neonatal period. Neonatal seizures are a common neurological problem with a frequency of 1.5-14/1000 neonates. Neonatal seizure is common in this part of Bihar and there was paucity of data from this area. Identification of etiology will help in management there by reducing morbidity and mortality.**Materials and Methods:** This prospective study was done in NICU of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laherasarai, from October 2017 to October 2018. Term neonates with clinically identifiable seizure were included in the present study.**Results:** Of 259 studied neonates, 184 were males and 75 were females. 90 neonates had seizures within first 24 hours and 66 neonates had seizures on day 2. Perinatal asphyxia was seen in 180 neonates and septicaemia was seen in 52 neonates.**Conclusion:** Perinatal asphyxia was the most common cause for neonatal seizures in term neonates, followed by septicaemia and metabolic disturbances.**Keywords:** Neonatal seizures, perinatal asphyxia, septicaemia.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Neonatal seizures or neonatal convulsions are epileptic fits occurring from birth to the end of the neonatal period [1]. Neonatal seizures are a common neurological problem with a frequency of 1.5-14/1000 neonates. The seizures in neonates may manifest as paroxysmal alteration in motor, sensory, behavioural or autonomic dysfunctions [2]. Clinically, there are four seizure types: subtle, clonic, tonic, and myoclonic. Each one can be focal, multifocal, and generalized [3]. Etiologically, about 80-85% of neonatal seizures are symptomatic and rest are idiopathic. The most common cause is hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE); the other causes include haemorrhage, metabolic disturbances, and infections [4]. Seizures are often the first sign of neurological dysfunction in newborns [5]. Infants with neonatal seizures are at increased risk of morbidity and mortality. The babies who survive may have adverse effects on motor, cognitive, and behavioural development or epileptic complications in the later part of the life [6].

The present study was conducted to determine the etiological factors for neonatal seizures in our hospital. The result of the study will help in planning

management of neonatal seizure to improve the short term as well as long term outcome.

Methods

This prospective study was done in NICU of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laherasarai, from October 2017 to October 2018.

All the term neonates with clinically identifiable seizures before 28 days of life were enrolled in the study. Preterm neonates, babies with neonatal tetanus, and babies with obvious congenital malformation were excluded.

A detailed antenatal, natal, postnatal, and family history was obtained and documented in predesigned proforma. Diagnosis of HIE was based on history, physical examination, Apgar score, arterial blood gas, brain MRI brain or cranial sonography. Diagnosis of neonatal infection was based on clinical manifestations, sepsis screening tests and blood culture, CSF analysis. Metabolic disorders were considered as hypoglycaemia (serum glucose <40mg/dl), hypocalcaemia (Total serum Ca <8mg/dl in full term.), and hypomagnesaemia (serum magnesium levels < 1.5 mg/dl). Intracranial haemorrhages were

diagnosed by CT scan brain. The results were analysed by appropriate statistical methods.

Results

In the present study, 259 neonates with chief complaints of seizures were included. 184 (71.04%) were males and 75 (28.95%) were females. 163 (62.93%) neonates were between 37 to 39 weeks of gestation, while 96 (37.06%) neonates were between 40 to 41 weeks of gestation. 155 (59.84%) neonates had vaginal delivery and 104 (40.15%) neonates were delivered by caesarean section.

Onset of seizure was day 1 in 90 (34.7%), day 2 in 66 (25.57%), and day 3 of life in 25 (9.65%) neonates. The most common type of seizure seen was

focal clonic type (n=86, 33.2%); followed by subtle seizures (n=80, 30.88%), myoclonic (n=46, 17.76%), focal tonic (n=22, 8.49%), multifocal (n=15, 5.79%), and generalized tonic clonic type (n=10, 3.86%). Among the studied population, perinatal asphyxia was identified as the most common cause of neonatal seizure (n=180, 69.4%). This was followed closely by septicaemia (n=52, 20.07%). Other significant causes identified were hypocalcaemia (n=10, 3.88%), hypoglycaemia (n=14, 5.40%), hyperbilirubinemia (n=8, 3.08%), intracranial haemorrhage (n=12, 4.63%), brain malformations (n=8, 3.08%). While, 5 (1.93%) neonates had hypomagnesaemia and 3(1.15%) neonate had seizures due to lignocaine injection.

Table 1: Sex wise distribution of cases

Sex	Total	%
Male	184	71.04
Female	75	28.95
Total	259	100

Table 2: Distribution of cases according to onset of seizures

Day of onset	Number of patients	%
1	90	34.7
2	66	25.57
3	25	9.65
4	16	6.17
5	6	2.31
6	12	4.63
7	13	5.01
>=8	31	11.96
Total	259	100

Table 3: Distribution of seizure according to the type of seizures

Type of seizure	Number of patients	%
Focal clonic	86	33.2
Subtle	80	30.88
Myoclonic	46	17.76
Focal tonic	22	8.49
GTCS	10	3.86
Multi focal	15	5.79
Total	259	100

Discussion

Neonatal seizures are a common neurological problem with a frequency of 1.5-14/1000 neonates. Etiologically, about 80-85% of neonatal seizures are symptomatic and rest are idiopathic. The most common cause is hypoxic-ischemic encephalopathy (HIE); the other causes include haemorrhage, metabolic disturbances, and infections [4].

In our present study, 184 (71.04%) neonates were male and 75 (28.95%) were females with male predominance 2.4:1 (table no 1). This finding was in contrast to the studies done by the Sahana G et al [7], Sabzehei MK et al [3], Parvin R et al [8] and Moayedi A.R et al [9] probably due to ignorance of the society which is still too much gender biased

ultimately leading to less admission rate of female babies altogether. 155 (59.84%) babies with neonatal seizure were born through the vaginal delivery and 104 (40.15%) babies were through the LSCS. This was found more or less similar with the study done by Sabzehei MK et al[3] (53% and 47% respectively).

Of the 259 neonates with seizures, 90 (34.7%) had seizures on day 1 followed by 66 (25.57%) on day 2 of life, 25 (9.65%) on day 3, and 31 (11.96%) on day >=8 days of life. A total of 181 (69.88%) neonates had seizures within first 3 days of life (table 2). Similar findings was found by the Sahana G et al⁷ and Ronen Gabriel et al [10]. Based on clinical seizure types, 86 (33.2%) neonates had focal clonic

type followed immediately by the subtle seizures in 80 (30.88%). Myoclonic type of seizures was seen in 46 (17.76%), focal tonic type in 22 (8.49%) and multifocal type in 15 (5.79%) neonates. This was found in concordance with the study done by Aziz A et al [11] and Verma YS et al [12] (table no 3).

Perinatal asphyxia was the most common cause of neonatal seizures identified in 69.4% (n=180) of neonates. This was found to be in concordance with the study done by Verma YS et al [12] (70%). In other studies, done by Najeeb S et al [13] (46%), Sabzehei MK et al[3] (34%), Glass HC et al [14] (38%) and Malik BA et al [15] (35%) of neonates had seizures due to hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy. In the present study 52 (20.07%) of 259 babies had sepsis (septicaemia and meningitis). This was found similar to the study done by Parvin R et al [8] (26%, n=51), Sabzehei MK et al[3] (24.4% n=102) and was found to be (29%) by the study done by Najeeb S et al[13]. In another study done by Malik BA et al 15 34% of babies had septicaemia. In the present study 4 (1.54%) baby had herpes infection as the cause for seizure which was found similar to the study done by Parvin R et al [8] (1.96%)

Seizures due to hypoglycaemia in association with comorbidities like HIE, Septicaemia and IDM were accounted for 23 (8.88%) whereas 14 (5.40%) babies had seizure only due to hypoglycaemia without any comorbidities. This was seen in concordance with the study done by Kumar A et al⁵ (11.11%), Sahana G et al[7] (9.17%). This is probably because of depletion of glycogen storage and inadequate feeding during early post-natal days. Seizures due to hypocalcaemia associated with other comorbidities like perinatal asphyxia, septicaemia and IDM were 65 (25.09%) babies, whereas isolated hypocalcaemia causing seizures were found in 10 (3.86%) of the 259 neonates studied. This was found similar to the study done by Parvin R et al[8] 15.65% (n=51) and Taksande A M et al[16] (n=110) where they found to be 11.8% and Verma YS et al[12] found it to be 11.67% (n=60). In 5 (1.93%) cases neonatal seizure was caused by hypomagnesaemia. Similar finding was seen by Taksande A. M et al [16]. Seizures due to hyperbilirubinemia (kernicterus) was seen in 8 (3.08%) neonates in the present study. Similar findings were found in study done by Najeeb S et al[13] (n=6, 6%). 12 (4.63%) neonates had seizures due to intracranial haemorrhage. Similar findings were seen by Najeeb S et al [13] (n=100, 4%) and Sudia S et al[17] (n=90, 4.6%). Seizures due to lignocaine toxicity was seen in 3 (1.15%) neonate in our study, similar finding was seen by Malik BA et al[15] (n=2, 1%).

Conclusion

The present shows perinatal asphyxia is the most common cause of neonatal seizures among term

neonates in our setup. The other causes followed in order are septicaemia, metabolic (hypoglycaemia, hypocalcaemia, hypomagnesaemia and hyperbilirubinemia), intracranial haemorrhages and brain malformations. Early identification of at risk pregnancies, institutional delivery and aseptic precautions with timely resuscitation is recommended to reduce morbidity and mortality due to neonatal seizures.

Declarations: Funding: None

References

1. Panayiotopoulos CP. The Epilepsies: Seizures, Syndromes and Management. Oxfordshire (UK): Bladon Medical Publishing; 2005. Chapter 5, Neonatal Seizures and Neonatal Syndromes. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK2599/>
2. Das D, Debbarma S. A Study on Clinico- Biochemical Profile of Neonatal Seizure. Journal of Neurology Research, North America, 6, dec. 2016. Available at: <http://www.neurores.org/index.php/neurores/article/view/404/399>. Date accessed: 20 May. 2017.
3. Sabzehei MK, Basiri B, Bazmamoun H. The Etiology, Clinical Type, and Short Outcome of Seizures in Newborns Hospitalized in Besat Hospital/Hamadan/ Iran. Iran J Child Neurol. 2014 Spring;8(2):24-8.
4. Kang SK, Kadam SD. Neonatal Seizures: Impact on Neurodevelopmental Outcomes. Front Pediatr. 2015 Nov 23;3: 101. doi: 10.3389/fped.2015.00101. eCollection 2015.
5. Kumar A, Gupta A, Talukdar B. Clinicoetiological and EEG profile of neonatal seizures. Indian J Pediatr. 2007 Jan;74(1):33-7.
6. M Levene. The clinical conundrum of neonatal seizures. Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed. Mar 2002;86(2):F75-F77. doi:10.1136/fn. 86. 2. F75.
7. Sahana G, Anjaiah B. Clinical profile of neonatal seizures. International journal of medical and applied sciences. Jan-March. 2014, Volume 3 Issue 1 page 21-27.
8. Parvin R, Afmsalim, Rahman M, Chowdhury K, Sultana A, Ahmed S, et al. Neonatal Seizures: Correlation between Clinico- Etiological Profile and EEG Findings. Bangladesh J Child Health 2014; Vol 38 (1): 19-23.
9. Moayedi, AR; Zakeri, S.; Moayedi, F. Neonatal seizure: etiology and type. Iranian Journal of Child Neurology, [S.l.], v. 2, n. 2, p. 23-26, nov. 2008. ISSN 2008-0700. Available at: <http://journals.sbm.ac.ir/index.php/ijcn/article/view/458>. Date accessed: 17 Dec. 2014.
10. Ronen GM, Rosales TO, Connolly M, Anderson V E, Leppert M. Seizure characteristics in chromosome 20 benign familial neonatal convulsions. Neurology. 1993 Jul; 43(7):1355-60.
11. Aziz A, Gattoo I, Aziz M, Rasool G. Clinical and etiological profile of neonatal seizures: a

- tertiary care hospital based study. *Int J Res Med Sci.* 2015; 3:2198-2203.
12. Verma YS, Dutt R, Rajput N, Patil R. Predictive value of EEG for neurodevelopmental outcome in neonatal seizures". *Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences* 2013; Vol2, Issue 29, July 22; Page: 5417- 5425.
 13. Najeeb S, Qureshi AM, Anis-ur-Rehman, Ahmad F, Shah S, Khan AY, et al. Aetiology and types of neonatal seizures presenting at Ayub Teaching Hospital Abbottabad. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad.* 2012 Jan-Mar; 24(1):33-7.
 14. Glass HC, Shellhaas RA, Wusthoff CJ, Chang T, Abend NS, Chu CJ. Et al. Contemporary Profile of Seizures in Neonates: A Prospective Cohort Study. *J Pediatr.* 2016 Jul; 174:98- 103.e1. doi:10.1016/j.jpeds.2016.03.035. Epub 2016 Apr 19.
 15. Malik BA, Butt MA, Shamoan M, Tehseen Z, Fatima A, Hashmat N. Seizures etiology in the newborn period. *J Coll Physicians Surg Pak.* 2005 Dec; 15(12):786-90.
 16. Taksande AM, Krishna V, Manish Jain, Mahaveer L. Clinico-biochemical profile of neonatal seizures. *PaedOncall Journal* 2005 October; 2(10). Available from: <http://www.pediatricall.com/Journal/Article/FullText.aspx?articleid=737&type=J&tid=&imgid=&reportid=326&tbltype=>
 17. Sudia S, Berwal PK, Nagaraj N, Jeavaji P, Swami S, Berwal A. Clinicoetiologiical profile and outcome of neonatal seizures. *Int J Contemp Pediatr* 2015;2:389-90.